

Article

ZigBeeNet: Decrypted Zigbee IoT Network Traffic Dataset in Smart Home Environment

Nur Keleşoğlu ^{*,†}

Institute of Theoretical and Applied Informatics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Bałtycka 5, 44-100 Gliwice, Poland; lsobczak@iitis.pl

* Correspondence: nkelesoglu@iitis.pl

† These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract: The number of smart homes is increasing steadily. One of the first technologies that comes to mind when talking about smart homes is Zigbee, which stands out for its low cost, low latency, low power consumption, and mesh networking capabilities. One of the key features of Zigbee is the encryption of payloads within its frames for security purposes. However, being able to decrypt this payload is crucial for fully understanding its operation and for purposes such as testing the network's security. Therefore, in this paper, we present the decrypted Zigbee IoT Network Traffic dataset, ZigBeeNet. We captured packets using Wireshark in real time from a smart home with 15 Zigbee devices over 20 days and saved them in pcap files. Additionally, we used a key extraction method to obtain the network key, decrypt the payload data, and analyze the characteristic features of network traffic, which we present in this paper. ZigBeeNet will be useful in wider areas than existing datasets with its ability to support network security research, pattern analysis, network performance analysis, and Zigbee traffic generator. We believe that this open-source dataset will contribute significantly to a wide range of industrial and academic research applications.

Keywords: Zigbee; smart home; IoT; network traffic; decrypted dataset; key extraction; network key; network traffic characteristics

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1. Introduction

Nowadays, the number of smart homes is rapidly increasing. According to Statista, it is estimated that the number of smart home users will be 785.16 million in 2028 [1]. Along with smart homes, the number of smart devices, their intended uses, and the applications developed are also increasing day by day. Zigbee is the most common wireless mesh networking technology for connecting sensor control systems and providing two-way communication in a wireless personal area network (WPAN) [2]. Thus, Zigbee is one of the most essential communication protocols for smart homes. There are commonly used protocols in smart homes, such as Z-wave for sensors, home automation, Wi-Fi for smart televisions and cameras, Bluetooth for smartphone-connected devices, and Matter for voice assistants. When we compare Zigbee with other widely used communication protocols, Zigbee supports energy-efficient communication between devices [3], relays, actuators, and other devices in the network because it allows a large number of devices to be connected to the network at the same time (up to 65,000 devices). The Zigbee protocol, designed for low-power, low-data-rate wireless communication, is widely used in smart home devices, industrial automation, and other Internet of Things (IoT) applications, even in automated guided vehicles [4] and for medical sensors [5]. As its popularity grows, so do concerns regarding the security and reliability of the data transmitted over Zigbee networks. Understanding the structure of Zigbee data packets and ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of the payloads are crucial for ensuring secure communication in these networks.

One of the key features of Zigbee is the encryption of data payloads within its frames, using a link key and a network key to ensure secure transmission. By encrypting the

payload, Zigbee prevents unauthorized access to sensitive information, such as device commands or sensor readings. However, for analytical purposes, being able to decrypt these data is essential for understanding the full scope of the network's operation. The ability to decrypt the Zigbee frames offers several significant advantages. Decrypted data can be used for many different purposes. The data can be used to identify the device's status [6], examine system operation, detect errors, and conduct performance analysis. This helps to analyze user behavior and habits in smart homes. For example, the brightness of the lights in a smart home or the temperature setting of the thermostat.

Analytical modeling, simulation, and actual deployment are the most common methods used to analyze the performance of smart home communication systems. However, decrypted data from Zigbee devices opens new possibilities for enhancing this analysis. By leveraging such data, machine learning models can be trained to make more accurate predictions about the system's behavior, helping to optimize device interactions and improve overall efficiency. In addition, for security reasons, decrypted data can be used to understand how an attack occurs and then take action. For this reason, it is critical to detect and fix security vulnerabilities and make systems more secure.

In this paper, we focused on creating a comprehensive dataset representing traffic in a Zigbee network. Zigbee communication, like most wireless protocols, employs encryption to secure transmitted data, which presents challenges in accessing and analyzing the detailed structure of network traffic. In most papers, the prepared or used dataset does not contain a decrypted payload due to not having extracted the network key. In our case, we were able to decrypt not only the transmitted traffic but also the payload of individual messages by using the link key and capturing the network key. This level of insight allows for an accurate representation of Zigbee's communication flows. The primary aim of this research is to investigate Zigbee network traffic characteristics. Since Zigbee is a protocol used for low-power and low-data-rate WPANs, researching Zigbee network traffic characteristics is important for security, privacy, efficiency, power consumption, and network performance. Also, understanding the characteristics of Zigbee network traffic is essential, especially in distributed systems such as large-scale networks and IoT. For example, latency analysis to improve network performance; anomalous traffic detection and testing of encryption protocols to find security vulnerabilities; and traffic density and distribution analysis, data flow types, payload content, etc., to model traffic or generate Zigbee traffic. The investigation of network traffic characteristics plays a major role in these analyses. For this reason, we believe that our dataset will serve a wider area than the purpose of the existing datasets (energy depletion attacks and network security, Zigbee network security of smart homes, and intrusion detection systems). It also allows for a deep understanding of Zigbee network traffic and IoT device behaviors and to study the network structure.

Our main motivation for studying the traffic characteristics of the network is the development of the Zigbee traffic generator and its critical role in testing and evaluating network systems. A realistic IoT traffic generator can simulate various traffic scenarios, providing researchers with a controlled environment in which to test network protocols, security features, and the performance of IoT devices without requiring extensive physical deployment. For example, there is a study that emphasizes the problem of predicting traffic from IoT devices [7]. With the increasing use of IoT devices, simulating various traffic scenarios is becoming more important, and traffic generators play a major role in this stage. Such a tool is crucial for identifying vulnerabilities, optimizing system performance, and ensuring robust security, particularly in Zigbee networks, which are widely used in home automation and industrial applications. Our decrypted dataset provides the foundation needed to model authentic traffic patterns, paving the way for the creation of a reliable and practical Zigbee traffic generator. The main contributions of this paper to the literature and industry are as follows:

- We present a novel and open-source smart home dataset of decrypted Zigbee IoT traffic, which is collected from a real IoT network over 20 days using various Zigbee devices.

- We describe the method of extracting the network's encryption key.
- We emphasize the importance of the decrypted dataset and analyze the characteristics of the network traffic that can be used to develop a Zigbee traffic generator in the future.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we review the related work, next we compare Zigbee with the other protocols in Section 3. In Section 4, we provide an in-depth overview of Zigbee to better understand its fundamental aspects, including its architecture, networking, data transmission, and security mechanisms. Then, we describe the data collection process and network key extraction in Section 5. In Section 6, we explain in detail the smart home environment and Zigbee devices where data are captured. In Section 7, we first describe the data postprocessing state, and then present our dataset with details of the captured traffic and network traffic characteristics. Then, we provide a discussion in Section 8, and finally conclude the paper in Section 9.

2. Related Work

Zigbee technology, with its low power consumption and expandable network structure, is widely used in smart home systems for applications such as smart lighting control systems [8–10], smart thermostats, security systems [11], smart locks, energy management systems, smart home assistants [12], and automation [13]. Thus, large amounts of data often need to be collected and analyzed to understand network traffic in smart homes, ensure security, and ensure efficient operation of systems. We now briefly review the previous studies in the literature that required and used Zigbee datasets.

First, we provide an example of using a decrypted Zigbee network traffic dataset. Ref. [6] presents two use cases of a Zigbee network traffic dataset. The first case involved using the data to identify the type of smart home device. The packets from the dataset were categorized, and features (e.g., packet length) were extracted for each category. These features were then fed into a machine-learning classification model. As a result, it was possible to detect the type of device (such as smart sockets or motion sensors) based on encrypted data. The second use case focused on identifying the device's status. In this case, the dataset needed to be decrypted and was used solely for training purposes. This allowed the classifier to accurately recognize the status transmitted by each device (e.g., motion detection). Such information can, in turn, be used for the analysis of users' daily behavior. In contrast to the above study, we aim to understand the network performance by decrypting the payload in the packets and extracting the characteristics of the traffic in order to develop a Zigbee traffic generator in the next stage. In addition, we would like to emphasize that our dataset can also be used in device status identification studies.

Second, we present previous security research on the Zigbee protocol and devices. In the study in [14], traffic between multiple Zigbee sensors (door, motion sensor, etc.) devices was decrypted. The experiments investigated how attackers could interpret this traffic, and the data packets sent by the sensors were analyzed. In this way, it was revealed how attackers could monitor the building's security system and how they could exploit the security vulnerabilities of the Zigbee protocol, and the precautions that could be taken against these vulnerabilities were evaluated. In the study in [15], they experimented with using IoT light bulbs to demonstrate the security vulnerabilities of Zigbee devices. With the help of Wireshark, the network key was captured, and the communication between the Trust light bulb was decrypted using this key. The above studies focused on the security vulnerabilities of the Zigbee protocol and the security vulnerabilities of Zigbee devices. Although our network key extraction is very similar to study [14], our purposes for using the dataset are not similar. In contrast to the above studies, we aim to decrypt the packets in the traffic to obtain the payload and analyze the network traffic.

Finally, we want to mention existing IoT network traffic datasets. The CIC IoT dataset [16] contains traffic from IoT devices connected in an LAN network. In contrast to our approach, this dataset is focused on packets transmitted between devices and the cloud solutions of individual manufacturers. Our solution, on the other hand, operates within

the Zigbee network, capturing raw packets exchanged within the mesh network. However, comparing our dataset to other Zigbee datasets, we can distinguish three other examples.

The Zigbee attack experimental dataset [17] consists of Zigbee packets from WIDS sensors during energy depletion attack experiments. CyLab Security and Privacy Institute supported this study. Four experiments were performed to test against an energy exhaustion attack launched by ATUSB using four Zigbee devices with CR2450 lithium batteries. Zigbee packets were captured between 29 April 2021 and 2 May 2021 for three days. The packets were captured and saved to pcap files. The network key for encryption is shared with the dataset, so decrypting the payload in the dataset is possible by using this shared key. This study was conducted to specify work on energy depletion attacks and network security.

The other dataset, CRAWDDAD cmu/zigbee-smarthome Data [18], was created by capturing the network traffic generated by ten Zigbee devices that can be found in smart home environments. A total of eight different experiments were conducted by changing the physical topology of the devices. Zigbee packets were captured between 24 February 2020 and 28 February 2020. These experiments were conducted at the Silicon Valley campus of Carnegie Mellon University to analyze the Zigbee network security of smart homes. One of the most important features of this dataset is that it includes encryption keys used to facilitate packet analysis in the dataset. Thus, the payload of the packets can be seen after entering the key. In contrast to these two datasets, the dataset we present in this paper consists of real-time network traffic captured from a total of 14 different Zigbee devices of eight different types over three weeks in a real smart home environment.

The other publicly available Zigbee dataset, ZBDS2023 [19], is created for IoT intrusion detection systems. The dataset was presented in Ref. [20] and captured from 30 June 2022 to 11 July 2022 for ten days from four different locations in a house with 10 Philips Hue devices in the smart home by four sets of Raspberry Pi CC2531s. The dataset contains raw pcap files. The dataset was created to detect five types of attacks. In contrast to our dataset, their dataset was developed for IDS systems and detection algorithms.

We give the existing Zigbee datasets and our dataset as a summary in Table 1. As can be seen in the table, although open-source datasets are shared, the ZBDS2023 dataset [20] is not decrypted. The cmu zigbee dataset [18] consists of data collected from 10 different devices in an experimental environment for 4 days and is used only for network security analysis. Although the Zigbee attack experimental data [17] is both decrypted and publicly shared, it was collected for 3 days for energy depletion attacks and network security. When the features of all these datasets are evaluated, the ZigBeeNet dataset stands out with its 15 devices, its gathering of real traffic data from real smart homes in real time for 20 days, its decryption, and its open-source sharing.

Table 1. Zigbee network traffic datasets.

Dataset	Area of Use	Period	Device Type	Decrypted	Public Shared
ZigBeeNet	Network traffic characteristics, Zigbee traffic generator	23 September 2024–14 October 2024 (20 days)	15 IoT Zigbee devices	Yes	Yes
Zigbee attack experimental data [17]	Energy attack	29 April 2021–2 May 2021 (3 days)	WIDS sensors	Yes	Yes
cmu zigbee [18]	Analyzing security	24 February 2020–28 February 2020 (4 days)	10 Zigbee devices	Yes	Yes
ZBDS2023 [20]	IoT intrusion detection systems	30 June 2022–11 July 2022 (10 days)	10 Philips Hue lights	No	Yes

3. Zigbee and Other Protocols Commonly Used in Smart Homes

Alongside presenting a new decrypted Zigbee dataset in this paper, we also address the fact that we chose Zigbee technology among many protocols used in smart homes

in line with our motivation. There are many commonly used communication protocols in smart home environments, such as Zigbee, Z-Wave, Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and Matter. We compare Zigbee with the other four commonly used protocols for smart homes. Table 2 presents the features of the communication protocols in terms of the number of devices, range, area of use, features, security, and price.

Zigbee is a wireless communication protocol based on the IEEE 802.15.4 standard and mesh networking technology. Mesh networking technology allows each device on the network to act as a router for other devices on the network. It is designed especially for smart home applications such as sensors, door locks, IoT applications, and home automation. Zigbee is a low-cost and low-data-rate protocol [21], the support range is up to 100 m, and it can support up to 65,000 devices in the same network [22]. It has a long battery life, consumes a low amount of power, and is cost-effective. Zigbee takes a short time (15 ms or less) to change the device's mode [13]. Also, Zigbee protects data using an encryption key, thus providing security.

Table 2. Smart home communication protocols.

Communication Protocol	Number of Devices/Range (m)	Areas of Use	Features	Security	Price
Zigbee	65,000/100 m	Sensors, door locks, home automation	Low power consumption, long battery life	Encryption key	Cost effective
Z-Wave	232/30 m	Sensors, thermostats, home automation	Low power consumption, long battery life	Encryption on standard	High cost
Wi-Fi	250/100 m	Smart TVs, cameras	High power consumption	Encrypted	Cost effective
Bluetooth	20/10 m	Smartphone-connected devices	Low latency, energy efficient	Encrypted	Low
Matter	-/100 m	Voice assistant	Low power consumption	Secure	Cost effective

Another protocol, Z-wave, was initially developed in 2001 by the company Zensys [23]. Z-Wave is another wireless communication protocol which is generally for home automation, such as sensors and thermostats, and has around a 30 m range [24,25]. It supports up to 232 nodes in the network [26]. It supports low power usage and long battery life. In Z-Wave technology, the security of both the network and the devices is ensured with the S2 protocol. On the other hand, Z-Wave devices have a limited number of manufacturers; however, with the licensing and certification fees, it is very costly compared to Zigbee.

Wi-Fi has higher power consumption compared to other protocols because Wi-Fi has a high data rate. It has a range of up to 100 m and about 35 m indoors [25]. Wi-Fi is mostly used for home appliances such as monitoring doors, management power outlets, and alarms [24]. Wi-Fi needs to use a strong radio frequency for large data transfer (video, camera images). Battery-operated devices and sensors consume a lot of energy for the transmission. For this reason, Wi-Fi technology is not suitable for smart home devices with sensors. In addition, Wi-Fi networks use encryption protocols to secure data, but they cover a large area. Therefore, Wi-Fi is more vulnerable to attacks.

Bluetooth is a protocol for IoT applications based on the IEEE 802.15.1 standard [25], which is implemented by Ericsson. It provides low latency and is enhanced for a short range of around 10 m. It is generally used in PCs, laptops, mice, keyboards, scanners,

printers, and digital cameras to exchange data. Bluetooth 5 uses encryption protocols, but the widespread use of Bluetooth by many devices can lead to security vulnerabilities.

Matter is a new communication protocol which has been developed by the Connectivity Standards Alliance (CSA). Matter, a unifying standard, aims to enable smart home devices from various manufacturers to work together. Thus, devices from different brands will have the potential to work together to organize smart home ecosystems. Matter offers applications such as voice control, bright lighting, and home entertainment systems. The number of connected devices varies depending on the router and bridge device used in the Matter protocol. Matter's coverage area also varies according to the technology used, but we can generally say 100 m. Matter also has a strong security infrastructure. However, very few devices fully support Matter [27], which is a new standard. In short, it is not used widely today, but its use will increase in the coming years, and it will provide convenience for smart homes.

In summary, we compare Zigbee with other widely used communication protocols in terms of areas of use, number of devices that can connect to the network, security, price, and features. When creating a smart home environment, we planned to use devices such as smart lights, smart bulbs, motion sensors, and wall switches. We decided to use Zigbee technology because it is the most efficient and compatible protocol for sensors in IoT-based smart home systems. Mainly, it allows a large number of devices to be connected to the network at the same time (this feature will be very significant in the coming years because the number of sensors used in smart homes in the coming years may reach thousands). Then, it has a long battery life, has an easily accessible market, consumes a low amount of energy, provides a secure network, thanks to the encryption key feature, and is cost-effective. In addition, Zigbee supports a range of up to 100 m, making it more useful than Bluetooth and Z-Wave in smart homes. In addition, Zigbee is more suitable for smart homes compared to the other low-power and low-latency protocol Bluetooth, thanks to its mesh networking feature compared to Bluetooth's limited mesh range in smart homes. In addition, its capacity to support up to 65,000 devices will be more useful in smart homes in the future as the number of sensors used increases. As we mentioned above, since Matter is not yet a widely used protocol, it may be difficult to use with many devices (sensors, smart bulbs, etc.). Although the number of devices that can be connected to the Wi-Fi network and its range is quite good, it is not a very suitable protocol for sensors used in smart homes because it consumes a high amount of power. Thus, we chose the Zigbee protocol for use in smart homes.

4. Fundamentals of Zigbee

Zigbee is a widely used wireless communication protocol tailored for low-power, low-bandwidth devices. Its primary applications are in the Internet of Things (IoT), smart home automation, industrial control systems, and wireless sensor networks. This section provides an in-depth look into the fundamental aspects of Zigbee, including its architecture, network formation, data transmission, and security mechanisms. The discussion is divided into three key subsections: Zigbee Network Structure, Zigbee Communication Process, and Zigbee Data and Security.

4.1. Zigbee Network Structure

The Zigbee protocol consists of four layers [28]. The Zigbee protocol operates on the IEEE 802.15.4 standard, which specifies physical (PHY) and medium access control (MAC) layers. Zigbee defines the network (NWK) and application (APL) layers, enabling it to offer scalable and flexible solutions for wireless communication. Zigbee networks consist of three types of devices: the coordinator, router, and end device. The coordinator is the central node responsible for network creation, management, and security settings, including distributing the network key for encryption. Routers extend the network range by forwarding data packets and can also allow new devices to join the network. End devices, typically battery-operated sensors or actuators, are designed to conserve energy

by sleeping between transmissions and are unable to forward packets. This multi-tier structure allows Zigbee to support a large number of devices while maintaining low power consumption and efficient communication.

Moreover, the Zigbee network can operate in one of three primary topologies: star, tree, or mesh. Figure 1 shows different types of network topologies based on wireless Zigbee. In the star topology, all devices (end devices) communicate through a central coordinator, while in the tree topology, (end) devices communicate via a hierarchical structure of routers. Mesh topology, the most robust, allows devices (called nodes) to communicate directly with each other, extending the network range and enhancing fault tolerance by enabling multiple communication paths. Thus, the Zigbee protocol generally uses mesh topology in smart homes.

Figure 1. Zigbee network topologies.

In Zigbee, device addressing is hierarchical, with the coordinator assigned the first address, followed by routers and end devices. The coordinator initiates the network by assigning a unique 16-bit address to each device joining the network. Additionally, Zigbee supports up to 65,536 nodes in a single network, making it highly scalable. The hierarchical structure of Zigbee's addressing system, combined with its flexible topologies, ensures that networks can be dynamically expanded without sacrificing performance or reliability.

4.2. Zigbee Communication Process

The process of communication in a Zigbee network begins with the network initialization and joining procedure, followed by data transmission and reception. When a Zigbee device powers on, it scans for available networks using a process called active scanning. During this process, it listens to beacon frames broadcast by the coordinator or routers, which contain information about the network's identity, channel, and capacity for new devices. Once a suitable network is found, the device requests to join. The coordinator or router evaluates the request and, if accepted, assigns a network address to the device.

A critical part of the joining process is the secure distribution of the network key, which ensures that only authorized devices can participate in encrypted communication within the network. When a new device joins the network, the coordinator sends the network key to the device using a secure key exchange mechanism. This exchange typically employs a pre-shared key (PSK) or a link key established during device pairing. The network key itself is encrypted using the pre-shared key to protect it from interception. Once the device successfully receives the encrypted network key, it decrypts it using the PSK, allowing it to communicate securely with other devices in the network.

This initial network key exchange is crucial for maintaining network security. Without it, unauthorized devices could potentially intercept or inject data into the communication stream. After the network key is successfully exchanged, the joining device can participate in encrypted communication, ensuring that data payloads are protected from eavesdropping or tampering. Additionally, network key updates may occur periodically or when the security of the network is compromised. These updates are also encrypted and securely distributed to all devices within the network, maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of the communication over time.

Once the network is formed and devices are connected, data are transmitted using a simple yet effective routing protocol. In mesh topology, Zigbee implements the Ad hoc On-demand Distance Vector (AODV) routing algorithm, which dynamically builds routing tables based on current network conditions. This allows Zigbee networks to self-heal, as alternative paths are discovered automatically when a link fails. End devices communicate with each other through either direct or indirect data transmission. Direct communication occurs when two devices are within range, while indirect communication involves routing through the coordinator or routers. Acknowledgments and retransmissions ensure data reliability, even in environments with interference or packet loss.

4.3. Zigbee Data and Security

Data in Zigbee networks are transmitted in the form of frames, with a layered structure that supports efficient and secure communication. A Zigbee frame consists of several key components: the header, which includes addressing information; the payload, which contains the actual data; and the footer, which carries error-checking information such as the frame check sequence (FCS). The payload is the core of the data frame, containing application-specific data, sensor readings, or commands. To maintain efficiency and low power consumption, Zigbee frames are compact, and their payloads are designed to carry only essential data.

Security is a major concern in Zigbee networks, particularly given the increasing deployment of these systems in critical applications such as smart grids and home automation. Zigbee incorporates several security features to protect data transmission and prevent unauthorized access. The most fundamental layer of security is encryption, which is applied to the data payload using the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) with 128-bit keys. Encryption ensures that the contents of the payload remain confidential, even if the data frame is intercepted by malicious entities.

A crucial aspect of Zigbee's security model is the use of network and link keys. The network key is shared by all devices in the network and is used to secure communication between them. The link key, on the other hand, is used for securing communication between specific pairs of devices and provides an additional layer of security. When a device joins the network, the coordinator distributes the network key in an encrypted form, ensuring that only authenticated devices can participate in the network. This key exchange process is fundamental to ensuring that unauthorized devices cannot intercept or manipulate the data being transmitted.

In addition to encryption, Zigbee employs message integrity codes (MICs) to ensure the integrity of the data. The MIC is appended to the data frame to verify that the payload has not been tampered with during transmission. Furthermore, Zigbee supports replay protection mechanisms, which prevent attackers from resending captured data frames to disrupt the network. These combined security features make Zigbee a robust and secure protocol for wireless communication, even in environments where security is a primary concern.

In summary, the Zigbee protocol's structure, communication process, and security mechanisms work together to provide a reliable and efficient solution for IoT applications. Its use of flexible topologies, energy-efficient communication, and strong security measures make it an ideal choice for applications requiring low-power wireless connectivity across large, scalable networks.

5. Methodology

In this section, we first explain the data collection process. Then, we describe the network key extraction method to decrypt the payload data.

5.1. Data Collection

The data collection process involved capturing Zigbee communication using a Texas Instruments CC2531 USB dongle, which allowed us to sniff and investigate the traffic in Wireshark. The data collection process is illustrated in Figure 2. The collecting process required that the packet sniffer was connected to a Raspberry Pi 3, which served as the data collection platform. Wireshark, running on the Raspberry Pi, was configured to capture all data from the sniffer on channel 11 (channel of the current Zigbee network configuration) and save it into pcap files. To manage the large volume of data, the recording was set up to save each hour of Zigbee network traffic into a separate pcap file. This data capture process was conducted continuously over 20 days. Additionally, remote access to the Raspberry Pi was configured, allowing for real-time monitoring and management of the data collection process. This setup ensured that the data capture proceeded without interruptions and that any issues could be addressed promptly. The collected packets were saved as pcap files. Each pcap file consisted of approximately one hour.

Figure 2. Process flow diagram of the data collection.

The data collection process may be affected by some bias due to hardware and software limitations. Specifically, Wireshark may introduce inaccuracies in data collection, for example, due to limited resources on the host computer, which can lead to packet loss. This may also occur if Wireshark restarts between data recording sessions or following a crash, interrupting the continuity of data capture. In addition, the placement of the sniffer in the smart home environment could impact the accuracy of packet capture. To reduce this effect, we placed the sniffer in a central part of the house to better capture network traffic across the entire space. This position was chosen to avoid areas with potential signal loss or interference that could lower capture quality. Despite these efforts, a small fraction of packets, representing 1.1% of the total dataset, were captured incorrectly. This minor error suggests that while the data collection method was generally reliable, factors like device placement and technical limitations should still be considered when interpreting the results.

5.2. Network Key Extraction

Additionally, it is necessary to perform key extraction to decrypt the network traffic. In Zigbee networks, there are two types of keys: the transport key and the network key. The transport key is publicly known and facilitates the initial communication between devices. Still, it is used to decrypt the headers of Zigbee's messages, and it cannot be used to decrypt the main data payload. The network key, on the other hand, is used to secure the majority of network traffic and is essential for decrypting the encrypted data payloads. To obtain the network key, we added a new device to the Zigbee network and captured the traffic during the pairing process. During this process, the coordinator transmits the network key to the new device in a special data frame. Using the packet sniffer, we were able to intercept this key. With the network key in hand, we could successfully decrypt the previously encrypted payload data. This allowed us to extract meaningful information

from the devices, such as motion detection events, ambient light levels, or specific color settings for smart bulbs, enabling us to build a comprehensive and detailed dataset.

6. Zigbee Smart Home Dataset

In this section, we present the decrypted Zigbee IoT network traffic dataset, ZigBeeNet. We collected IoT network traffic in real time between 23 September 2024 and 14 October 2024 over 20 days. The dataset is publicly available for download and use in a study. We have released the ZigBeeNet dataset via our GitHub repository at <https://github.com/iitis/ZigBeeNet> (accessed on 20 October 2024) and in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13957307>) (accessed on 20 October 2024) [29]. The folder is 1.64 GB in size and consists of 501 pcap files. We also provide the Zigbee network key with the dataset. All detailed explanations on how to download the dataset, which devices we use, how to open the dataset (Wireshark, extract data collection stage, etc.), and network key configuration are available in our GitHub repository. In the rest of this section, we present the Zigbee devices used in the smart home and describe the smart home where the dataset was collected.

6.1. Zigbee Devices

We used 15 devices in total, 6 different types of devices (hub, power plug, smart light, smart bulb, wall switch, and motion sensor) and 9 different devices. Table 3 shows the devices that were used in the smart home to collect data. All devices were connected to the network by Zigbee. Our device list was as follows: A Hue Bridge; a Hue smart plug; two Hue white and color ambiance Play light bars and a Hue Go for smart lights; two Hue white and color ambiance bulbs, three Hue white ambiance bulbs, and two Lidl Livarno RGB bulbs for smart bulbs; two Hue dimmer switches for walls; and a Hue motion sensor. Moreover, a Hue Go, two Hue dimmer switches, and a motion sensor were powered by a battery. Other devices were connected to mains power. The combination of battery-powered and non-battery-powered devices increases the diversity of the dataset.

Table 3. List of Zigbee devices used in smart home.

No.	Device Type	Device Name	Number of Devices	Battery Powered
1	Hub	Hue Bridge	1	No
2	Power Plug	Hue Smart Plug	1	No
3	Smart Light	Hue White and Color Ambiance Play	2	No
		Hue Go	1	Yes
4	Smart Bulb	Hue White and Color Ambiance Bulb	2	No
		Hue White Ambiance Bulb	3	No
		Lidl Livarno RGB Bulb	2	No
5	Wall Switch	Hue Dimmer Switch	2	Yes
6	Motion Sensor	Hue Motion Sensor	1	Yes

6.2. Smart Home Environment

One of the most essential features of the dataset we present is that it is real-time smart home IoT network traffic. Rather than synthetic data in the laboratory or virtually, this paper collects the dynamic IoT network traffic of a house equipped with smart Zigbee devices where four people live. Figure 3 shows the location of probes and devices in the smart home environment. The house consists of two floors, each approximately 60 square meters. The left side of the figure illustrates the ground floor of the house, and the right side of the figure shows the first-floor plan of the house. Additionally, at the bottom side,

the names of the devices used are given with their images. The computer for data collection is located on the first floor in bedroom 2.

Figure 3. Plan of the smart-home installation.

The even distribution of Zigbee devices inside the home enabled a practical evaluation of the Mesh network's performance. Analysis of the collected IoT traffic confirmed that only 22.2% of packets were transmitted directly between devices without retransmission within the mesh network, highlighting the network's reliance on intermediate nodes for packet delivery. This result demonstrates that the network uses a mesh routing to maintain connectivity between devices. Further details on this behavior are discussed in Section 7.2.6.

7. Zigbee Network Traffic Dataset and Its Characteristics

In this section, we first explain the data postprocessing stage after gathering data. Then, we analyze the Zigbee network traffic characteristics based on the decrypted data.

7.1. Data Postprocessing

The collected dataset consists of multiple pcap files capturing Zigbee network traffic. During initial inspection, some files were found to be corrupted, displaying the following message: "The capture file appears to have been cut short in the middle of a packet" when opened in Wireshark (Figure 4). This issue likely resulted from incomplete packet captures, which could hinder subsequent analysis.

The issue arises from an incorrectly decoded data packet signaling the end of transmission, which causes the recording data to stop and the pcap file to close suddenly without the proper file termination. To address this, a postprocessing step was necessary. First, a custom script was developed to re-save each pcap file using the `editcap` tool, which helped repair any malformed packets and ensured the integrity of the packet captures. Once the individual files were corrected, they were merged into a single comprehensive pcap file using the `mergcap` tool. This allowed for more efficient analysis of the entire dataset as a unified whole.

Figure 4. Example of a corrupted packet capture file in Wireshark.

For the purposes of temporal analysis and to simplify further processing, the merged pcap file was then divided into equal one-hour segments using `mergecap`. This segmentation facilitated time-based exploration of the data while maintaining manageable file sizes for analysis.

This postprocessing pipeline was essential to ensure the consistency and usability of the dataset, enabling more reliable and structured analysis of Zigbee network traffic in subsequent stages of the research. Figure 5 shows how all the packets look in Wireshark when we open the pcap file. The file is 1.64 GB in size, and Wireshark requires 10 GB RAM to open the file. As seen in the figure, Wireshark, by default, displays the following seven columns: no., time, source, destination, protocol, length, and info.

Figure 5. Overview of the dataset in Wireshark.

7.2. Network Traffic Characteristics

The Zigbee network traffic dataset consists of 24,679,823 packets in total. The first packet was captured on 23 September 2024 at 22:53 (GMT+2) in Poland, and the last packet was captured, and stopped capturing, on 14 October 2024 at 18:18 (GMT+2). The total time elapsed was recorded as 20 days, 20 h, and 4 min. Thus, since 24,679,823 packets were collected in approximately 30,004 min, an average of 822.55 packets were captured per minute: 13.7 packets per second. The data byte rate was measured at 516 bytes per second, and the data bit rate was 4134 bits per second. The total data size captured was 930 MB, with an average packet size of 37.69 bytes.

7.2.1. Packet Density Analysis

When examining the network traffic characteristics, packet density analysis provides important information about the performance of a network. For example, the number of packets sent and received provides information about the network traffic density. If there is a large difference between the number of packets sent and received by a device, it may mean that there is a problem with the device. Another example is related to instantaneous peaks; instantaneous increases in the number of packets can occur when more than one device is transmitting data at the same time, and the capacity of the network can be exceeded at these times. In general, packet density analysis is an effective analysis for observing the traffic density on the network and measuring its capacity.

Figure 6 shows the graphs of the number of packets in the network (a) per second, (b) per minute, and (c) per 10 min. The x-axis in the figures represents time in seconds, and the y-axis represents the number of packets. When we look at Figure 6a, we observe that the number of packets in the network increases rapidly every second at certain, non-fixed intervals. In Figure 6b, these peak points are seen more clearly. In Figure 6c, we see that the average number of packets every 10 min is around eight thousand. These three sub-figures show the number of packets at different intervals. In Figure 6c, the oscillation is very high, but in (b) and (a), the increase in the number of packets can be easily observed. The traffic density in the network has increased at these times. The results of such analyses lead to the next stage of investigating why the traffic density has increased at these time intervals. The traffic of each network may differ, so the analysis of packet density at different time intervals is important.

7.2.2. Packet Length Analysis

Packet length is the amount of information carried by each data packet on a network and is usually measured in bytes. We divided packet length into three groups: short, medium, and long packets. The lengths of short, medium, and long packets were defined as between 0 and 19 bytes, 20 and 79 bytes, and 80 and 159 bytes, respectively. There are 9,987,365 short packets in the dataset. Short packets are generally acknowledgment (ACK), data requests, or control messages. There are 13,572,619 medium packets in the dataset, and medium-length packets generally indicate standard data exchanges, such as sensor readings and data transmission. Long packets can contain more complex data in addition to image/sensor data. These may be bulk data or device software updates. In the dataset, there are 1,119,839 packets. Long packages constitute 4.53% of the total number of packages.

7.2.3. Packet Distribution by Device

Table 4 shows the number of packets sent directly by each device, excluding retransmissions. Figure 7 illustrates the distribution of packet numbers across different types of devices. The Hue Bridge, from the hub category, generates the most traffic, accounting for 43.4% of the total, as expected due to its routing role in the Zigbee network.

Most lamps and bulbs contribute 2% to 5% of the traffic. An exception are bulbs from another manufacturer, each responsible for around 10%. This could be due to an implementation of the Zigbee protocol or to their location in the farthest corner of the house, potentially requiring more retries for reliable communication.

Battery-powered devices (wall switches and a motion sensor) generate the least traffic (0.1% to 0.5%), as they minimize communication to conserve energy.

(a) Graph of the number of packets per second.

(b) Graph of the number of packets per minute.

(c) Graph of the number of packets per 10 minutes.

Figure 6. Combined figure: (a–c) illustrate the graph of the number of packets in the dataset per second, per minute, and each 10 min, respectively.

Figure 7. Zigbee traffic distribution by device type.

Table 4. Number of packets sent by each device on the network (without retransmitted packets).

Device Type	No	Device Name	Address	Number of Packets	Percentage
Hub	1	Hue Bridge	0xd7a7	3,257,732	43.4%
Power Plug	2	Hue Smart Plug	0xe7f5	243,766	3.3%
Smart Light	3	Hue White and Color Ambiance Play #1	0xe46c	374,103	5.0%
	4	Hue White and Color Ambiance Play #2	0xc370	384,155	5.1%
	5	Hue Go	0xc9b3	366,791	4.9%
Smart Bulb	6	Hue White and Color Ambiance Bulb #1	0x1de6	370,916	4.9%
	7	Hue White and Color Ambiance Bulb #2	0xb85c	360,000	4.8%
	8	Hue White Ambiance Bulb #1	0xa163	212,195	2.8%
	9	Hue White Ambiance Bulb #2	0xe8eb	206,929	2.7%
	10	Hue White Ambiance Bulb #3	0x8a76	207,384	2.8%
	11	Lidl Livardo RGB Bulb #1	0xdfef	747,588	10.0%
	12	Lidl Livardo RGB Bulb #2	0x9f06	725,862	9.7%
Wall Switch	13	Hue Dimmer Switch (upstairs)	0x6395	5597	0.1%
	14	Hue Dimmer Switch (downstairs)	0x69bd	5388	0.1%
Motion Sensor	15	Hue Motion Sensor	0x2a30	28,291	0.4%

7.2.4. Packets Distribution by Network Layer

The dataset contains 24,679,823 captured packets and the captured traffic is distributed across different layers of the Zigbee protocol stack, which is built on the IEEE 802.15.4 standard. Zigbee operates in the lower layers (physical and MAC) defined by IEEE 802.15.4,

and the higher layers consist of the Zigbee Network layer (NWK) and application layer protocols like Zigbee Device Profile (ZDP) and Zigbee Home Automation (ZHA). The packet breakdown is as follows:

- IEEE 802.15.4 packets: A total of 10,343,419 packets (41.9%) are at the IEEE 802.15.4 layer, which includes operations at the MAC layer such as channel access and frame control.
- Zigbee Network packets: A total of 6,636,492 packets (26.9%) belong to the NWK layer, handling tasks like device addressing and routing within the mesh network.
- Zigbee Device Profile packets: A total of 29,989 packets (0.1%) correspond to the layer used for device discovery and management.
- Zigbee Home Automation packets: A total of 7,669,923 packets (31.1%) are related to the ZHA layer, which is used for communication and data exchange between smart home IoT devices.

Figure 8 presents a pie chart visualizing the proportion of packets across different layers. This distribution highlights the importance of the Zigbee Home Automation layer; with nearly one-third of the traffic dedicated to smart home devices, it contains the most significant data from an end-user perspective.

Figure 8. Zigbee traffic distribution by network layer type.

7.2.5. Broadcast vs. Unicast

The dataset comprises a total of 27,394,823 packets, with 5,401,398 packets (21.9%) classified as broadcast messages and 19,278,425 packets (78.1%) as unicast messages. This predominance of unicast traffic highlights the typical communication patterns in Zigbee networks, where direct device-to-device communication is preferred.

To further explore broadcast traffic, we categorized packets based on different Zigbee layers, as shown in Figure 9, which presents a pie chart of overall broadcast traffic (a). The results are as follows:

- IEEE 802.15.4 broadcast packets: 151,110 packets (1.5%)
- Zigbee NWK broadcast packets: 5,096,603 packets (76.8%)
- Zigbee ZDP broadcast packets: 18,640 packets (62.2%)
- Zigbee HA broadcast packets: 135,045 packets (1.8%)

These findings indicate that while unicast messages dominate Zigbee communication, broadcast packets represent a significant portion, particularly within the Zigbee NWK layer. This distribution is further illustrated in Figure 9, which presents a bar chart detailing broadcast packets across various Zigbee protocol layers (b).

Figure 9. Comparison of (a) broadcast vs. unicast and (b) broadcast packet distribution by Zigbee layer.

7.2.6. Packet Transmission Analysis

In this subsection, a detailed analysis of the packet distribution within the captured Zigbee network traffic is presented. Specifically, the focus is on the proportion of packets originating from devices (source packets), packets retransmitted by intermediate devices (relay packets), and packets transmitted directly between devices (direct packets). This analysis is conducted across three distinct layers: Zigbee NWK, Zigbee ZDP, and Zigbee HA. The insights are based on a comprehensive breakdown of packet traffic and can be visualized through Figure 10 which illustrate the packet distribution across the layers.

(1) Overall Packet Distribution Across Zigbee Layers

Across all layers above or equal to the Zigbee stack, we observed a total of 14,336,403 packets. Of these, 52.3% were source packets, while 47.7% represented retransmitted packets. Direct packets, i.e., packets transmitted directly from one device to another without intermediate retransmission, made up 22.2% of the overall traffic. This indicates a significant reliance on retransmission mechanisms within the Zigbee network, likely due to the inherent nature of mesh networking protocols (Figure 10a).

- Source packets: 7,496,697 packets (52.3%);
- Relay packets: 6,839,706 packets (47.7%);
- Direct packets: 3,181,136 packets (22.2%).

(2) Packet Distribution in the Zigbee NWK Layer

Focusing solely on the Zigbee NWK layer, which forms the fundamental communication framework for all Zigbee devices, we observed a total of 6,636,492 packets. The majority of these packets (64.8%) were retransmitted by intermediate devices, highlighting the extensive role of relaying in maintaining connectivity within this layer. Direct communication, on the other hand, was minimal, accounting for only 0.1% of the traffic (Figure 10b).

- Source packets: 2,333,492 packets (64.8%);
- Relay packets: 4,302,999 packets (35.2%);
- Direct packets: 7269 packets (0.1%).

(3) Packet Distribution in the Zigbee ZDP Layer

Within the Zigbee Device Profile layer, which facilitates management and control functionalities such as device discovery and binding, we captured a total of 30,335 packets. Source packets accounted for 23.4% of the traffic, while relay packets made up the bulk,

contributing 76.6%. Direct communication at this layer remains negligible, constituting only 1.2% of the total traffic (Figure 10c).

- Source packets: 7019 packets (23.4%);
- Relay packets: 22,970 packets (76.5%);
- Direct packets: 346 packets (0.1%).

(4) Packet Distribution in the Zigbee HA Layer

The Zigbee Home Automation layer, responsible for communication between devices in smart home environments, exhibited a significantly different distribution of packet types compared to other layers. Out of 7,669,923 packets, a significant portion (41.4%) were direct packets, reflecting the nature of home automation systems, where devices often communicate directly. In contrast, relay packets comprised 32.8% of the traffic, while source packets accounted for 67.2% of all packets (Figure 10d).

- Source packets: 5,156,186 packets (67.2%);
- Relay packets: 2,513,737 packets (32.8%);
- Direct packets: 3,173,521 packets (41.4%).

Figure 10. Packet transmission by network layer type: (a) overall, (b) Zigbee NWK, (c) Zigbee ZDP, (d) Zigbee HA.

The analysis of packet distribution across the various Zigbee layers reveals distinct communication patterns. While the Zigbee NWK and ZDP layers rely heavily on retransmission, the Zigbee HA layer shows a preference for direct communication, likely due to the topology and proximity of devices in home automation environments. This variability in packet transmission behavior is crucial for understanding the efficiency and reliability of Zigbee-based networks in different applications.

7.2.7. Message Types and Layers

In this section, we analyze the percentage distribution of packet types based on the protocol layer. The dataset used for this analysis includes various message types observed in the IEEE 802.15.4, Zigbee NWK, ZDP, and HA layers. The distribution of packet types across these layers provides insights into the structure and behavior of Zigbee network traffic.

(1) IEEE 802.15.4 Layer

At the IEEE 802.15.4 layer, the majority of traffic consists of acknowledgment (ACK) messages, which are crucial for ensuring reliable communication in the network. Below is the breakdown:

- ACK: 9,484,056 packets (91.9%);

- Data request: 524,684 packets (5.1%);
- Data: 243,481 packets (2.4%);
- MLE: 57,118 packets (0.5%);
- Reserved: 4716 packets (0.1%).

The overwhelming dominance of ACK messages (nearly 92%) reflects the importance of confirming data transmissions in Zigbee networks (Figure 11a).

(2) Zigbee NWK Layer

At the Zigbee NWK layer, the primary message types are related to routing operations, with route request and route record messages forming a significant portion of the traffic:

- Route request: 3,954,354 packets (59.7%);
- Route record: 1,494,214 packets (22.5%);
- Link status: 1,142,182 packets (17.2%);
- APS ACK: 36,962 packets (0.6%).

This layer’s traffic is heavily focused on route discovery and maintenance, essential for mesh networking in Zigbee environments (Figure 11b).

(3) Zigbee ZDP Layer

At the ZDP layer, the traffic consists of control and network management messages, where network address request and response dominate:

- Network address request: 17,485 packets (58.3%);
- Network address response: 9454 packets (31.5%);
- Device announcement: 1623 packets (5.4%);
- Match descriptor request: 986 packets (3.3%);
- Others: 441 packets (1.5%).

These packets are critical for managing the addressing and discovery functions in the network; most of them are responsible for providing the network address (Figure 11c).

Figure 11. Packet type distributed by network layer type: (a) IEEE 802.15.4, (b) Zigbee NWK, (c) Zigbee ZDP, (d) Zigbee HA.

(4) Zigbee HA Layer

The Zigbee HA layer handles messages related to device interaction and control, such as attribute readings and responses. The message distribution reveals heavy traffic in commands related to color and level control:

- Read attributes color control response: 1,572,441 packets (20.5%);
- Read attributes color control: 1,375,916 packets (17.9%);
- Read attributes manufacturer-specific response: 1,178,953 packets (15.4%);
- Read attributes manufacturer-specific: 961,510 packets (12.5%);
- Read attributes on/off: 526,775 packets (6.9%);
- Read attributes on/off response: 513,430 packets (6.7%);
- Read attributes level control: 524,053 packets (6.8%);
- Read attributes level control response: 510,048 packets (6.7%);
- Others: 506,797 packets (6.6%).

The Zigbee HA layer shows a high volume of attribute reporting and responses, particularly related to lighting control (color control and on/off commands), reflecting the network's use in smart lighting applications (Figure 11d).

The analysis of network traffic across different layers reveals the distinct roles that each layer plays in the Zigbee protocol stack. While the IEEE 802.15.4 layer is dominated by ACK messages, ensuring communication reliability, the Zigbee NWK layer focuses on routing, and the ZDP layer manages network addresses and device discovery. The Zigbee HA layer shows extensive use of commands related to device control, particularly in lighting, with color control and on/off commands being the most prevalent. This distribution offers valuable insights into the communication patterns and the functional focus of the Zigbee network in the dataset.

7.2.8. Power Source Distribution of Traffic

In this subsection, we analyze the distribution of network traffic based on the power source of the Zigbee devices, focusing on devices powered by batteries and those connected to mains power. This analysis is critical for understanding how power source impacts communication patterns and network behavior.

(1) Power Source Distribution

To visualize the distribution of network traffic, a pie chart (Figure 12a) showing the percentage of packets originating from battery-powered and mains-powered devices was generated. In total, 601,463 packets (2.46%) were transmitted by battery-powered devices, while 23,843,029 packets (97.54%) came from AC-powered devices.

When considering the number of devices involved, with 3 battery-powered devices and 12 AC-powered devices, the average number of packets sent per device can be calculated. On average, each battery-powered device transmitted approximately 200,488 packets, while each AC-powered device transmitted about 1,986,919 packets (Figure 12b). This significant disparity highlights the higher communication frequency and load handled by AC-powered devices, likely due to their stable energy supply, enabling more sustained network activity.

(2) Traffic Involving Battery-Powered Devices

In addition to the overall distribution, we also examined the number of packets specifically transmitted from and sent to battery-powered devices. A bar chart (Figure 13) illustrates this comparison. Battery-powered devices sent 39,276 packets, while 38,155 packets were received by battery-powered devices. This relatively balanced traffic suggests a bidirectional communication pattern between battery-powered nodes and other network participants.

Figure 12. Power source distribution of Zigbee traffic: (a) % of packets by source power and (b) average number of packets per device.

Figure 13. Distribution of traffic for battery-powered devices.

This analysis of power-related traffic patterns provides valuable insights into the network dynamics, highlighting the dominant role of mains-powered devices in handling the bulk of communication, as well as the interaction between battery-powered devices within the Zigbee network. Such information is vital for optimizing energy-efficient communication protocols and maintaining network performance.

8. Discussion

The dataset with decrypted Zigbee payloads fills a key gap in current research by allowing detailed analysis of device communication and command patterns. Unlike existing datasets, it provides access to underlying data, enabling studies on network behavior, security vulnerabilities, and protocol reverse-engineering. This also opens up opportunities to evaluate the energy efficiency of smart devices, such as identifying whether lights remain on when no one is home, if they turn off too late after detecting motion, or if other devices are unnecessarily active. By analyzing such patterns, researchers can propose optimizations to reduce energy consumption, making IoT systems not only more secure but also more sustainable. This makes the dataset a valuable resource for advancing research in both the security and energy efficiency of Zigbee-based systems.

In this study, we present a novel decrypted Zigbee network smart home real traffic dataset. Our aim with this study is to provide a dataset to help investigate Zigbee network traffic characteristics. We provide a foundation for modeling real traffic patterns with our decrypted dataset. Thus, we allow researchers to generate network traffic by using the

dataset for many applications in the industrial field and in smart homes, such as testing different applications and detecting security vulnerabilities.

However, as in [20], the dataset we present is not specifically for an intrusion detection system. There is no attacker or post-injected attack in the dataset. Additionally, the dataset we present is suitable for network analysis but is not directly useful for analyzing network security, as the dataset in [20] is. Moreover, it is suitable for generating network traffic using a dataset. Thus, different types of traffic can be generated for any study and used to analyze network security or IDS.

Future Work

As the number and variety of smart devices used in smart home environments increase, simulation studies may become essential to verify system performance under higher network loads and the potential for further system development. In this context, developing a Zigbee traffic generator is necessary to better analyze situations such as different traffic loads, various usage scenarios, and security threats. A Zigbee traffic generator has practical applications, especially in IoT research and development. It allows testing and simulating Zigbee networks without needing real devices, making it possible to see how the system responds to different types of network traffic. This helps in finding issues and improving network performance. Additionally, a packet generator is useful for testing security by simulating attacks, which helps to identify and fix weaknesses. Lastly, such generators are valuable for machine learning, as they provide data to train systems that automatically detect unusual network behavior, improving security in IoT environments. For this reason, the authors plan to work on the Zigbee traffic generator in future work to simulate IoT and Zigbee network traffic based on the collected dataset. The presented ZigBeeNet dataset has great potential for developing the Zigbee traffic generator. The authors also plan to increase the number of IoT devices and their types in the smart home to make the dataset more comprehensive, allowing for the development of more universal solutions.

IoT network traffic includes more than just Zigbee communication. The Zigbee hub connects to a cloud server via the home LAN, enabling user access to devices from any location. Furthermore, the home network contains other IoT devices, such as cameras and sensors. Recording this wider range of traffic would create a more comprehensive dataset, beneficial for advancing research in IoT systems and security.

9. Conclusions

One of the significant features of Zigbee is that it encrypts the data payloads within the frame to ensure secure communication. This encryption is achieved using the link key and the network key and prevents unauthorized access to sensitive information such as device commands or sensor data. However, it is important to be able to decrypt these data to understand the full operation of the network and for analytical purposes or to understand how an attack occurs. Thus, we presented a publicly decrypted Zigbee real IoT traffic dataset for smart home applications. This dataset fills the gap in the literature for a decrypted Zigbee dataset. Another purpose of this study is to investigate Zigbee network traffic characteristics. Therefore, researchers are able to explore the feasibility of developing a reliable generator for simulating IoT and Zigbee network traffic.

We collected IoT network traffic data in a two-floor smart home. We used 15 Zigbee devices in total, six different types of devices (hub, power plug, smart light, smart bulb, wall switch, and motion sensor) and nine different devices. We obtained the network key, explained in detail in Section 5.2, to decrypt the payload data of each packet in the traffic. Then, we analyzed the Zigbee network traffic characteristics of our data in Section 7.

The analysis of the Zigbee network traffic dataset reveals several key characteristics. Packet distribution across network layers highlights the prominence of the Zigbee HA layer, particularly in supporting smart home devices, with nearly one-third of the traffic originating from this layer. While unicast messages dominate, broadcast packets play a significant role in the Zigbee NWK layer. The analysis of packet transmission shows a higher

tendency for retransmissions in the Zigbee NWK and ZDP layers, in contrast to more direct communication in the Zigbee HA layer. Furthermore, message types vary across layers, with the IEEE 802.15.4 layer primarily handling ACK messages to ensure communication reliability, and the Zigbee and ZDP layers focusing on routing and network management. The Zigbee HA layer, meanwhile, is responsible for device control, particularly in lighting systems. Finally, traffic analysis by power source distribution provides further insight into the operational aspects of the network. These findings collectively enhance the understanding of Zigbee network traffic characteristics in smart home environments. On the other hand, the fact that the data were collected only for 20 days with 15 IoT devices in a specific smart home may not adequately reflect variations such as heavy traffic conditions or security threats in the environments, even if we consider that it is a large dataset. For this reason, the authors plan to expand the dataset by increasing the number of devices, as mentioned, in future work.

Another proposal for future work is to develop a Zigbee traffic generator. A Zigbee traffic generator has many potential effects, such as testing possible security attacks or simulating different traffic densities. We want to emphasize that the development of the Zigbee traffic generator is not only a theoretical contribution but also can have a significant impact on practical applications. The dataset we present in this paper will help to develop a Zigbee traffic generator. We believe that our dataset makes a significant contribution to the literature and industrial applications.

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